

Development of a Continuous Flow Setup for the Synthesis of Ruthenium(II) Photosensitizers

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Abstract

Metal complex photosensitizers have become increasingly important for light-driven catalytic reactions such as water splitting, carbon dioxide reduction or the synthesis of value-added chemicals. Ruthenium(II) polypyridyl photosensitizers (PSs) are particularly interesting as they show favorable properties such as modular synthetic access, long lifetimes of the triplet excited state, suitable oxidation and reduction potentials in the ground as well as the excited state to split water, (photo)chemical stability, and tunable visible light absorption. Ru –based PSs are also important as fluorescence marker in medical diagnostics. To meet the demand for these complexes, this work explores the potential of continuous flow synthesis for the often-utilized $[\text{RuCl}_2(\text{tbbpy})_2]$ complex, a precursor for tbbpy-based bisheteroleptic Ru(II) polypyridyl complexes. A continuous flow setup was designed, constructed, and successfully commissioned. A kinetic sensitivity analysis revealed maximum yields of 56% at 170 °C, at a ligand/precursor ratio of 2:1, and a residence time τ of 6 minutes for the $[\text{RuCl}_2(\text{DMSO})_4]$ starting material. Kinetic analysis suggests that higher yields could be obtained with even harsher conditions and very short residence times. Compared to microwave batch experiments with a reaction time of 6 minutes, the continuous process showed a 5.6-fold increase in yield and a 7-fold increase in space-time yield. These results demonstrate the successful transferability of PS synthesis from batch to continuous processes, providing the foundation for extending the setup to multistep synthesis on the pathway to realize on-site recycling of Ru(II) PSs.

Introduction

The development of sustainable synthetic routes for high-value chemical compounds has emerged as a critical challenge in both academic research and industrial chemistry. Among these compounds, metal complex photosensitizers stand out as pivotal molecules for addressing global energy and environmental challenges through light-driven catalytic transformations. Ruthenium(II) polypyridyl photosensitizers (PSs) show exceptional photophysical and photochemical properties, exhibiting long-lived triplet excited states, favorable oxidation and reduction potentials in both ground and excited states, strong visible light absorption with tunable wavelengths, excellent photochemical stability, and most importantly, modular synthetic accessibility through the systematic variation of coordinated polypyridyl ligands.^[1-5] This unique combination of properties renders Ru(II) polypyridyl complexes indispensable for a diverse range of applications spanning from light-driven water splitting and carbon dioxide reduction to the catalytic synthesis of value-added organic chemicals.^[1-3] Beyond catalytic applications, these complexes have also proven invaluable as fluorescence markers in medical diagnostics, biosensing platforms, and photodynamic therapy agents, further underscoring their broad utility in contemporary chemistry and biomedicine.^[6,7]

The $[\text{RuCl}_2(\text{tbbpy})_2]$ complex (tbbpy = 4,4'-di-tert-butyl-2,2'-bipyridine) intermediate represents a crucial building block for the preparation of more elaborated bisheteroleptic Ru(II) polypyridyl complexes through ligand substitution reactions.^[8,9] The synthetic accessibility and reliable preparation of such precursors in high yield and purity are therefore essential prerequisites for the broader goal of enabling scalable synthesis of sophisticated photosensitizer architectures. Microwave-assisted methodologies applied for the synthesis of this precursor have been shown to afford $[\text{RuCl}_2(\text{L})_2]$ complexes with high selectivity and minimal side product formation when employing appropriately designed precursor complexes with chelating auxiliary ligands.^[10]

The increasing demand for Ru(II) polypyridyl photosensitizers, coupled with the inherent cost associated with ruthenium as a precious metal, has created both economic and sustainability imperatives for process optimization. Conventional batch synthesis protocols, while established and well-characterized, typically employ heated organic solvents under reflux or microwave heating for periods ranging from several hours to multiple days.^[8,10,11] Although microwave-assisted batch synthesis has substantially improved reaction times and yields compared to traditional thermal methods - reducing synthesis of $(\text{R-bpy})_2\text{RuCl}_2$ complexes from 72 to 1.5 hours with yields exceeding 90% - such approaches remain constrained by inherent limitations of batch operation, including inconsistent mixing, temperature gradients, and poor scalability.^[8,10,11]

The transfer of synthetic methodologies from batch to continuous flow platforms represents a powerful strategy to overcome these limitations.^[12] Continuous flow reactors leverage precise control over residence time, improved micromixing efficiency, superior heat transfer characteristics, and the ability to operate at higher volumetric throughputs - all factors conducive to enhanced process productivity and efficiency.^[9,13,14] For metal complex synthesis in particular, microreactor technology enables the application of harsher reaction conditions (elevated temperatures, hazardous intermediates, or reactive reagents) with superior safety profiles compared to corresponding batch operations.^[15]

The application of continuous flow technology to the synthesis of Ru(II) polypyridyl complexes remains substantially underdeveloped. The present work addresses this gap by exploring the transferability of photosensitizer synthesis from well-established batch protocols to continuous flow platforms, with the $[\text{RuCl}_2(\text{tbbpy})_2]$ complex serving as a prototypical target. This work is motivated by the dual objective of: (1) demonstrating the technical feasibility and advantages of flow-based Ru(II) complex synthesis through comprehensive sensitivity analysis and kinetic characterization, and (2) establishing a foundation for the subsequent integration of multistep synthetic sequences toward a future on-site photosensitizer recycling processes. By systematically optimizing process parameters including temperature, precursor stoichiometry, and residence time, we sought to identify conditions maximizing product yield and space-time yield while maintaining product quality. A direct comparison with state-of-the-art microwave batch procedures provides quantitative evidence of the advantages afforded by the continuous flow approach.

Results and Discussion

The development of the continuous synthesis setup aimed for process intensification following the high pressure and temperature approach. By applying pressure, the reaction solution can be heated above the boiling point, eventually accelerating the reaction. This was implemented with a continuous flow reactor, utilizing a capillary reactor with an inner diameter of 1/16" and an outer diameter of 1/8". The length of the reactor could be adjusted by installing capillaries with different lengths. This reactor was placed in a heated oil bath for tempering. The reactor could be operated with pressures of up to 6.8 bar. Reactants were supplied to the reactor by several pumps, which also could be used for adjusting the composition of the reaction solution by varying the ratio of the flow rates. An UV/vis flow-through cell was installed downstream to the reactor for online analysis of the reaction progress by following the formation of new bands associated with the formation of the metal complexes. More details on the implementation can be found in the Materials and Methods section and the ESI. The flow diagram of the setup is shown in Figure 8.

The synthesis of $[\text{RuCl}_2(\text{tbbpy})_2]$ (tbbpy = 4,4'-di-*tert*-butyl-2,2'-bipyridine) was studied in the developed reactor setup, with special focus on optimal reaction conditions for maximizing its yield over any side products as $[\text{RuCl}_2(\text{tbbpy})_2]$ is commonly used for later synthesis tris-bipyridine type Ru(II) photosensitizers with functional NN-chelate ligands. The introduction of the third ligand requires the substitution of the two monodentate chlorido-ligands which can be facilitated by adding significant amounts of water or utilization of $\text{AgPF}_6/\text{AgBF}_4$ salts. Such heteroleptic tris-bipyridine type complexes are highly interesting for applications, e.g. in light-driven catalysis, as they allow for fine-tuning of optical and redox chemical properties as well as the construction of multimetallic photocatalysts by introduction of an appropriate third NN-chelating ligand. For this, a mixture of the metal precursor, either polymeric $[\text{RuCl}_2(\text{COD})]_n$ (COD = cyclooctadiene) or $[\text{RuCl}_2(\text{DMSO})_4]$, was mixed in the setup with a solution containing tbbpy. This reaction solution was then fed to the reactor. As main parameters for the optimization of the complex formation, the reaction temperature and the reaction time were varied.

The standard precursor for the synthesis of $[\text{RuCl}_2(\text{tbbpy})_2]$ complexes in batch reactors is $[\text{RuCl}_2(\text{COD})]_n$. This precursor is insoluble in dimethylformamide (DMF), which was used as a solvent. Since capillaries with relatively large inner diameter were used, it was evaluated whether the standard procedure for synthesizing $[\text{RuCl}_2(\text{tbbpy})_2]$ can be directly transferred from a microwave-assisted batch to a continuous synthesis. In line with typical reaction conditions in batch, a suspension of $[\text{RuCl}_2(\text{COD})]_n$ was pumped through the reactor.

First stability trials were conducted for 2 different temperatures of 150 °C and 160 °C, with and without additional pressure (4 bar) (see Figure 1). These conditions were chosen to evaluate challenging operational conditions close to the boiling point of DMF. The

hydrodynamic residence time was set to 12.6 min. For all conditions fluctuations of the yields for the complexes containing two or three tbbpy ligands were observed. Since the fluctuations occurred synchronous for both products, i.e. $[\text{RuCl}_2(\text{tbbpy})_2]$ and $[\text{Ru}(\text{tbbpy})_3]\text{Cl}_2$, it was concluded that the fluctuations stem from the online UV/vis analysis due to the presence of suspended $[\text{RuCl}_2(\text{COD})]_n$ and the formation of vapor bubbles as a result of evaporation of the solvent at 150 °C. Applying an elevated pressure of 4 bar significantly reduced fluctuations even at an increased temperature of 160 °C, as a result of reduced bubble formation and increased solubility at higher temperatures. For a reaction temperature of 150 °C, steady state is reached after about 3 residence times, while operation for about 4 residence times was required for a reaction temperature of 160 °C. The large fluctuation of the yield at around 40 to 50 min is exemplary for operational issues with the suspension of the insoluble precursor, which partially blocked the back-pressure valve. This varies the effective residence time in the reactor and thus the yield recorded with UV/vis spectroscopy. When the valve opened (40 min) the effective residence time was reduced and thus the yield dropped. Later, the effective residence time first increased again when the flow stabilized (closing of the valve), before it changed to a steady value at around 50 min.

Figure 1: Stability test of the operation conditions with $[\text{RuCl}_2(\text{COD})]_n$ as precursor without and with an additional 4 bar back-pressure valve for an operation of about 70 min. Left: yield of $[\text{RuCl}_2(\text{tbbpy})_2]$ and right: yield of $[\text{Ru}(\text{tbbpy})_3]\text{Cl}_2$.

Based on these feasibility tests, the effect of temperature on the complex formation was studied for $[\text{RuCl}_2(\text{COD})]_n$ as starting material. Results are shown in Figure 2. A linear increase of the yield of $[\text{RuCl}_2(\text{tbbpy})_2]$ was found, while the yield of $[\text{Ru}(\text{tbbpy})_3]\text{Cl}_2$ showed no statistically significant increase. The formation of the homoleptic $[\text{Ru}(\text{tbbpy})_3]\text{Cl}_2$ gives evidence that small amounts of water were still present in the setup, even though the reactor was operated under inert N_2 atmosphere and commercial pre dried DMF was utilized.^[8,16] The presence of water is required to obtain $[\text{Ru}(\text{tbbpy})_3]\text{Cl}_2$ as it facilitates replacement of Cl^- . The

observation that the yield of $[\text{Ru}(\text{tbbpy})_3]\text{Cl}_2$ does not change with temperature and stays between 5 to 8 % also gives evidence that the formation of this species does not follow a simple consecutive reaction pathway, but requires adjusted reaction conditions, e.g. the presence of water.

The results of the kinetic analysis are shown in Figure 2 left (see Materials and Methods section for details). The simulations show reasonable agreement with the experimental data, suggesting that the chosen kinetic model is plausible. The determined kinetic parameters were further used for a sensitivity analysis on the reaction temperature and time to evaluate optimal reaction conditions for obtaining a maximal yield. A maximum yield of 48 % is expected for a reaction temperature of 124 °C and a residence time of almost 200 minutes. For higher reaction temperatures the decomposition of DMF limits the obtainable yield due to the release of CO and the formation of $[\text{RuCl}(\text{CO})(\text{tbbpy})_2]^+$ as undesired side-product (see below for a more detailed discussion).

Figure 2: Left: Yields of $[\text{RuCl}_2(\text{tbbpy})_2]$ (Ru_{II}) and $[\text{Ru}(\text{tbbpy})_3]\text{Cl}_2$ (Ru_{III}) for different temperatures at a residence time of 12.56 min and a ligand-to-Ru ratio of 3:1 for experiments with $[\text{RuCl}_2(\text{COD})]_n$ as starting material. Right: Predicted yield as function of temperature and reaction time.

Table 1: Kinetic parameters determined for experiments with $[\text{RuCl}_2(\text{COD})]_n$ as starting material.

Parameter	Value	Unit
$k_{1,\text{ref}}$	0.09	$\text{m}^3 \cdot \text{mol}^{-1} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$
$k_{2,\text{ref}}$	300.48	$\text{m}^6 \cdot \text{mol}^{-2} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$
$k_{3,\text{ref}}$	0.01	$\text{mol} \cdot \text{m}^{-3} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$
$k_{4,\text{ref}}$	32.61	$\text{m}^3 \cdot \text{mol}^{-1} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$
$E_{A,1}$	70.01	$\text{kJ} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$
$E_{A,2}$	32.19	$\text{kJ} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$
$E_{A,3}$	81.05	$\text{kJ} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$
$E_{A,4}$	12.80	$\text{kJ} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$

During these studies dosage problems with the used membrane pump were observed frequently. While the results show that it is in principle feasible to use $[\text{RuCl}_2(\text{COD})]_n$ as precursor also in a continuous setup, the practicability of this approach is strongly limited, and no further experiments were conducted with this precursor.

Due to the outlined issues with the insoluble $[\text{RuCl}_2(\text{COD})]_n$, $[\text{RuCl}_2(\text{DMSO})_4]$ was studied as an alternative, soluble Ru precursor. Beside this, the ligand-to-Ru ratio was adjusted to the desired ratio of 2:1 to favor the formation of $[\text{RuCl}_2(\text{tbbpy})_2]$. To increase process stability even further, the installed back-pressure valve was replaced by a valve that could be set to pressures of 6.8 bar. Stability tests are presented in Figure 3. Compared to results obtained with $[\text{RuCl}_2(\text{COD})]_n$, the stability of operation improved significantly. Even at temperatures up to 190 °C, i.e. about 40 °C above the boiling point of DMF at atmospheric pressure, the yields remained stable after an initial start-up phase. Stable yields were obtained after less than 2 residence times (25 min). Again, the trends observed for the two- and three-times substituted complexes are synchronized, giving evidence that the observed fluctuations during start-up, e.g. at about 10 min for a temperature of 170 °C, are caused by the start-up behavior of the setup. Again, the three-fold substituted species is observed with a yield of about 10-12 %, independent of the reaction temperature.

Figure 3: Stability test of the operation conditions with $[\text{RuCl}_2(\text{DMSO})_4]$ as precursor with an operational pressure of 6.8 bar for an operation of about 70 min. Left: yield of $[\text{RuCl}_2(\text{tbbpy})_2]$ and right: yield of $[\text{Ru}(\text{tbbpy})_3]\text{Cl}_2$.

The results of reaction time studies for a reaction temperature of 170 °C are shown in Figure 4 left. The reaction time was changed by adjusting the length and with this the volume of the reactor, while the flow rates were kept constant. After a fast increase of the $[\text{RuCl}_2(\text{tbbpy})_2]$ yield during the first minutes, a maximum is reached after 12 minutes. The formation of $[\text{Ru}(\text{tbbpy})_3]\text{Cl}_2$ is similar fast as the formation of $[\text{RuCl}_2(\text{tbbpy})_2]$ after 1 min of reaction time. After this, no significant changes of the yield were observed, which might relate to a complete consumption of water impurities in DMF. Water accelerates the formation of $[\text{Ru}(\text{tbbpy})_3]\text{Cl}_2$ by solvating Cl^- , freeing up free coordination spaces, which enables the coordination of a third tbbpy.

Figure 4: Left: time dependence of the $[\text{RuCl}_2(\text{tbbpy})_2]$ (Ru_{II}) and $[\text{Ru}(\text{tbbpy})_3]\text{Cl}_2$ (Ru_{III}) yield for a reaction temperature of 170 °C for experiments with $[\text{RuCl}_2(\text{DMSO})_4]$ as starting material and a ligand-to-Ru ratio of 2:1. Right: Temperature dependence of the yield of $[\text{RuCl}_2(\text{tbbpy})_2]$ and $[\text{Ru}(\text{tbbpy})_3]\text{Cl}_2$. Markers represent experimental data points, lines indicate results from simulations. Hollow marker represent results obtained upon addition of water to the reaction solution.

Table 2: Kinetic parameters determined for experiments with $[\text{RuCl}_2(\text{DMSO})_4]$ as starting material.

Parameter	Value	Unit
$k_{1,\text{ref}}$	0.98	$\text{m}^3 \cdot \text{mol}^{-1} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$
$k_{2,\text{ref}}$	300.48	$\text{m}^6 \cdot \text{mol}^{-2} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$
$k_{3,\text{ref}}$	0.01	$\text{mol} \cdot \text{m}^{-3} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$
$k_{4,\text{ref}}$	32.61	$\text{m}^3 \cdot \text{mol}^{-1} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$
$E_{A,1}$	154.79	$\text{kJ} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$
$E_{A,2}$	32.19	$\text{kJ} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$
$E_{A,3}$	81.05	$\text{kJ} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$
$E_{A,4}$	12.80	$\text{kJ} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$

While the reactor was operated under inert atmosphere with water free DMF, water might have been introduced to the system during preparation for experiments due to the strong hygroscopic properties of DMF. To test this hypothesis, water was added with 3 % of the reactant volume (10 mL) for an experiment at 170 °C (see Figure 4 right). A decrease of the $[\text{RuCl}_2(\text{tbbpy})_2]$ yield from about 58 % to 40 % is observed. In parallel, the yield of $[\text{Ru}(\text{tbbpy})_3]\text{Cl}_2$ increased from 10 % to 18 %, proving that water has to be present in the reaction solution to form the three-fold substituted complex. These results give further evidence that water was present in the system during experimentation.

In general, full conversion was not reached during the experiments. Furthermore, the mass balance for Ru could not be closed, as only about 65 % of Ru in the form of $[\text{RuCl}_2(\text{tbbpy})_2]$

and $[\text{Ru}(\text{tbbpy})_3]\text{Cl}_2$ were detectable. The single substituted complex $[\text{RuCl}_2(\text{DMSO})_2(\text{tbbpy})]$ only shows absorption in band in the UVC region, which is also not detectable by the applied UV/vis spectroscopy and thus limited detection of all Ru species. Independent from this analytical limitation, the single-substituted species should undergo a consecutive conversion towards the two-fold substituted species, which should be detectable for longer reaction times. Since the yield reached a maximum after 12.6 min, the presence of larger fractions of $[\text{RuCl}_2(\text{DMSO})_2(\text{tbbpy})]$ is excluded.

Some published synthesis procedure reported similar limitations of the yield for $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2\text{Cl}_2]$, at 60 to 80%.^[17,18] A possible limitation is the solvent DMF. DMF starts to decompose at $T > 153\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Decomposition results in the release of reactive CO into the reaction solution. In fact, this behavior is taken advantage of in carbonylation reactions at similar temperatures of 180-190 $^\circ\text{C}$. For carbonylation reactions, DMF serves as a cheap and readily available CO source.^[19,20] According to Clear et al., DMF decomposition also occurs when DMF is used as a solvent in thermal synthesis methods of ruthenium(II) PSs^[21]. Produced CO can lead to side product formation of $[\text{RuCl}(\text{CO})(\text{tbbpy})_2]^+$ with yields of 30-40 %^[21,22]. Complexes of $[\text{RuCl}(\text{CO})(\text{tbbpy})_2]^+$ type show absorbance below 460 nm^[23]. Therefore, possible $[\text{RuCl}(\text{CO})(\text{tbbpy})_2]^+$ was not detectable in the experiments since $\lambda = 460\text{ nm}$ and $\lambda = 565\text{ nm}$ were used for quantitative evaluation of the product streams. Thus, the missing 35 % of the total yield are attributed to the formation of the side product complex $[\text{RuCl}(\text{CO})(\text{tbbpy})_2]^+$.

Figure 4 right shows the results of a temperature sensitivity analysis. A maximum yield of about 58 % of $[\text{RuCl}_2(\text{tbbpy})_2]$ was found at a reaction temperature of 170 $^\circ\text{C}$. For higher temperatures, the yield of $[\text{RuCl}_2(\text{tbbpy})_2]$ decreases again, which is reasoned by the pronounced formation of $[\text{RuCl}(\text{CO})(\text{tbbpy})_2]^+$.

Kinetic simulations and experimental data show a good agreement, indicating that the assumed loss of Ru through formation of a CO species is a reasonable consideration. It can also be concluded that an intensification of the Ru-complex synthesis requires a further optimization of the temperature to minimize CO formation and with this increase the Ru-yield.

To analysis this, a theoretical sensitivity analysis was conducted with the established kinetic model and kinetic parameters by varying the reaction time in a range from 100 to 250 °C and the reaction time from 1 to 180 min. The results are shown in Figure 5 and indicate that the highest yield would be achievable at a temperature of 209 °C and a reaction time of 1.8 min. This optimum represents a compromise between the rate of complex formation and the rate of DMF decomposition. The short residence time is required to avoid a pronounced formation of CO and thus formation of the undesired $[\text{RuCl}(\text{CO})(\text{tbbpy})_2]^+$ species. While the

Figure 5: Maximum yield of $[\text{RuCl}_2(\text{tbbpy})_2]$ and $[\text{Ru}(\text{tbbpy})_3]\text{Cl}_2$ as function of temperature. The maximum yield was determined for different reaction times, but only the maximal value is shown for clarity.

parameterization of the kinetic model is based on only a few number of data points and therewith any predictions should be interpreted with care, the results point on a potent strategy to accelerate the formation of $[\text{RuCl}_2(\text{tbbpy})_2]$ even further. When also considering a reliable removal of water from the system, a yield of about 80 % is expected.

The transfer of the Ru-complex synthesis can be evaluated based on different performance indicators. The already discussed yield of the double-substituted complex is one of the key parameters. For a meaningful comparison, the batch synthesis using microwave-heating was conducted as well (see Materials and Methods section for experimental details). For $[\text{RuCl}_2(\text{COD})]_n$ and $[\text{RuCl}_2(\text{DMSO})_4]$ yields of 58 and 50 %, respectively, were obtained by following a similar procedure to the continuous one (see Figure 6). Reactions were conducted for 45 min. In comparison to this, a yield of 58 % was obtained in the continuous setup, but with a reaction time of only 6 min and a temperature of 170 °C. The high yields of more than 95 % reported in the literature could not be reproduced, most likely due to insufficient means to avoid water in the system under investigation.

Figure 6: Overview of measured and reported yields for different methods to synthesize $[RuCl_2(tbbpy)_2]$.^[8,17]

Figure 7 shows the yields obtained after 6 min reaction time for the microwave-assisted synthesis in batch with different solvents and for the continuous synthesis. This reaction time was chosen since the maximum yield is reached in the continuous approach at 170 °C for this time. While the batch approach resulted in yields in the range of 10 %, a yield of almost 60 % could be realized with the continuous approach, an intensification by a factor of 6. Likewise, the space-time-yield could be increased by the same factor, from 0.1 mmol m⁻³ s⁻¹ to 0.7 mmol m⁻³ s⁻¹ when transferring the synthesis of Ru complexes to a continuous flow synthesis.

Figure 7: Yields and space-time-yields for a reaction time of 6 min and different synthesis methods and solvents.

Conclusions and Outlook

In this work, the successful transfer of the batch synthesis of Ru-complexes from batch to continuous processing could be demonstrated. While the feasibility of this transfer could be demonstrated with $[\text{RuCl}_2(\text{COD})]_n$ as precursor, the practicability was limited due to blocking of the setup. Switching to $[\text{RuCl}_2(\text{DMSO})_4]$ as precursor allowed to overcome this limitation and resulted in stable operation. In comparison to a microwave-assisted batch synthesis of $[\text{RuCl}_2(\text{tbbpy})_2]$, similar yields were obtained in the continuous setup. The space-time-yield could be increased 6-fold, demonstrating the potential of the batch-to-continuous transfer.

Limitations observed with respect to the overall yield of $[\text{RuCl}_2(\text{tbbpy})_2]$ were reasoned by the undesired presence of water, which enabled the formation of $[\text{Ru}(\text{tbbpy})_3]\text{Cl}_2$. Furthermore, the decomposition of DMF was identified as a limiting factor, as it leads to the formation of CO, which eventually undergoes a reaction with Ru towards $[\text{RuCl}(\text{CO})(\text{tbbpy})_2]^+$. While this substance was not detectable with the available analytic methods, a reasonable agreement with the kinetic simulation supports this reaction step as a plausible reason for the unclosed mass balance.

Analysis of the obtained kinetic data indicates that control of the decomposition of DMF is the key for a high yield of Ru-complexes. To identify a suited reaction control strategy, kinetic studies on the temperature dependence of the DMF decomposition are required. Results from simulation suggest that operating at even higher temperatures in combination with very short reaction times allows to accelerate the complex formation even further. For this, a fast temperature reduction after the reactor is required, which can be realized in e.g. microreactors. With this, the decomposition and the subsequent formation of CO complexes might be restricted, which will be subject of upcoming studies. The use of microwave heating in a microreactor would be an alternative option for rapid heating and fast subsequent cooling. Alternatively, another high-boiling solvent, that does not decompose by releasing CO.

Materials and Methods

Chemicals

$[\text{RuCl}_2(\text{COD})]_n$, $[\text{RuCl}_2(\text{DMSO})_4]$, DMF, 4,4'-di-*tert*-butyl-2,2'-bipyridine (tbbpy) and acetone were purchased from Sigma Aldrich. Inert gas N_2 was purchased from MTI Industrial Gases. All chemicals were of commercial purity and used without further purification. The product samples for calibration measurements $[\text{RuCl}_2(\text{tbbpy})_2]$ and $\text{Ru}(\text{tbbpy})_3(\text{PF}_6)_2$ were synthesized according to the literature^[8]. This procedure was also used for comparative batch experiments with microwave heating.

Experimental Setup

Figure 8 shows the flow sheet of the continuous flow setup used for the synthesis of $[\text{RuCl}_2(\text{tbbpy})_2]$.

Figure 8: Process flow sheet of continuous flow synthesis setup.

The setup consisted of a capillary reactor (CR1), membrane pumps (P1, P2, P3), a controllable valve (VC1), a T-mixer (M1), a back pressure regulator (PR1), a cooler (C1), *in situ* UV/vis spectroscopy (UV1), a stirrer (ST1), and containers for the precursor, tbbpy, polymeric $[\text{RuCl}_2(\text{COD})]_n$ (COD = cyclooctadiene) or $[\text{RuCl}_2(\text{DMSO})_4]$ and dimethylformamide (DMF). Further parts are gas distributors (D1 and D2), multiple two and three way valves, and three bypass tubes (BP1, BP2 and BP3). As tubing material perfluoroalkoxy polymer (PFA) with 1/16" inner diameter and 1/8" outer diameter is used. For connections polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) flangeless fittings with UNF 1/4" 28 G thread are used.

Further information on the experimental procedures can be found in the electronic supporting information.

Kinetic Modelling

For the kinetic analysis, the reaction network R0-R4 was considered. X_n and X_m represent the ligands of the used precursor.

The following assumptions were made:

- 1) R0 is very fast and proceeds instantaneously. Thus, it was neglected in the kinetic description and $[\text{RuCl}_2X_m(\text{tbbpy})_2]$ was considered to be present with the same concentration as the precursor $[\text{RuCl}_2X_n]$ at the inlet of the reactor.
- 2) Reactions R1–R4 follow first-order kinetics with respect to all educts involved in the respective reaction and zero-order with respect to all other species.
- 3) Water is required in stoichiometric amounts for R3, thus the achievable concentration of $[\text{Ru}(\text{tbbpy})_3]\text{Cl}_2$ is equal to the initial concentration of water.
- 4) DMF as solvent is present in large excess. Its concentration is therefore considered constant, resulting in pseudo-zero-order behavior for reaction R3.
- 5) The kinetic parameters of R2-R4 are independent of the used precursor.

With these assumptions, the rate equations (1)-(4) are obtained. c_i is the concentration of component i . The dependence of the rate constants k_1 to k_4 on temperature T was implemented according to Arrhenius law in Eq. (5) with a reference temperature T_{ref} of 170 °C. $k_{j,\text{ref}}$ is the rate constant of reaction j at T_{ref} , $E_{A,j}$ the corresponding activation energy, and R the universal gas constant.

$$r_1 = k_1 c_{[\text{RuCl}_2X_m(\text{tbbpy})]} c_{\text{tbbpy}} \quad (1)$$

$$r_2 = k_2 c_{[\text{RuCl}_2(\text{tbbpy})_2]} c_{\text{tbbpy}} c_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} \quad (2)$$

$$r_3 = k_3 \quad (3)$$

$$r_4 = k_4 c_{[\text{RuCl}_2(\text{tbbpy})_2]} c_{\text{CO}} \quad (4)$$

$$k_j(T) = k_{j,\text{ref}} \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{E_{A,j}}{R} \left(\frac{1}{T} - \frac{1}{T_{\text{ref}}}\right)\right) \quad (5)$$

The yield of component i at residence time τ , Y_i , was calculated using the steady state plug flow reactor mass balance in Eq. (6). $c_{[\text{RuCl}_2\text{Xn}]_0}$ is the initial precursor concentration and ν_{ij} describes the stoichiometric coefficient of component i in reaction j .

$$\frac{dY_i}{d\tau} = \frac{1}{c_{[\text{RuCl}_2\text{Xn}]_0}} \sum_{j=1}^4 \nu_{ij} r_j \quad (6)$$

To estimate the kinetic constants, Eqs. (1)-(6) implemented in Python 3.13 and the differential equations were numerically solved using the solver LSODA^[24]. The kinetic parameters were obtained by minimizing the mean squared error between the simulated and experimental yields using a Sequential Least Squares Programming optimizer^[25]. The full implementation is available at https://gitlab.uni-ulm.de/ag-ziegenbalg/kinetic_model_continuous_ru_ps_synthesis.^[26]

For $[\text{RuCl}_2(\text{DMSO})_4]$, $k_{j,\text{ref}}$ was first determined using the residence time resolved yields at 170 °C. Subsequently, the activation energies were determined based on the yields at $\tau = 12.56$ min and varying temperature. For $[\text{RuCl}_2(\text{COD})_4]$, $k_{1,\text{ref}}$ and $E_{A,1}$ were adjusted to match the experimental yields, while all remaining kinetic parameters were adopted from the $[\text{RuCl}_2(\text{DMSO})_4]$ kinetic.

With the parameterized model, the optimum temperature and ideal residence time were determined based on a sensitivity analysis of both variables to obtain the maximum achievable $[\text{RuCl}_2(\text{tbbpy})_2]$ yield.

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Electronic Supporting Information

Electronic supporting information are available online.

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